

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**RISK FACTORS OF ANXIETY AND DEPRESSION DURING
PREGNANCY****¹ Dr Saira Waqqar, ² Dr Javeria Masahal, ³ Dr Gul Muhammad, ⁴ Dr. Tohmassub
Tayyab, ⁵ Dr Asif Butt**¹Senior Lecturer, Riphah International University²PG Trainee, DHQ Hospital Rawalpindi.³Senior Lecturer, SIMDC, Lodhran.⁴Assistant Professor, UOL .⁵Lecturer, Rawalpindi Medical University.**Abstract:****Objectives:** The aim of study was to identify level of depression & anxiety during pregnancy and its associated risk factors.**Materials & Methods:** A Case-Control study was conducted from February to July 2018 at DHQ Hospital Mianwali, THQ Hospital Talagang and Obaid Noor Hospital Mianwali. 581 pregnant women were selected by Non probability purposive sampling technique. Data was collected through self-structured questionnaire, Hospital Anxiety Depression Scale (HADS) and the Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS). SPSS 21 was used for data analysis.**Results:** Five eighty one pregnant women were enrolled. Mean age of participant was 25.93±4.06. The majority of women were house wives (94.5%) and only (5.5%) were working women. Majority of participants belongs to middle class (60.9%) while only (11.2%) women belong to high class socioeconomic status. The Mean Anxiety score was 7.23±3.27 and Mean Depression score was 7.35±2.83 (using HADS). It was found that out of 581 participants (33.21%) cases were report with anxiety and (30.46%) cases reported with depressive symptoms. On the other hands results of estimates risk factors show that Antenatal Anxiety having higher odds ratio with Family crises (6.97;CI: 4.57-10.64), Fear of Baby Girl (2.59;CI: 1.008-6.68), History of miscarriage (1.78;CI: 1.15-2.74) and Fear of C-Section (1.50;CI: 1.007-2.24). And antenatal Depression having higher odds ratio with Family crises (5.46;CI:3.62-8.25),Fear of baby girl(3.75;CI:1.43-9.86), History of miscarriage (2.31;CI:1.49-3.57) and Fear of C-Section(1.78;CI:1.11-2.68).**Conclusion:** Study findings show mild to moderate Frequency of anxiety & depression during pregnancy. Risk factors such as; Fear of C-Section, Gender discrimination, family crises and history of miscarriage was associated with severity of antenatal anxiety & depression.**Keywords:** Antenatal Anxiety & Depression, Prevalence, Risk Factor, Multidimensional scale of perceived social support,**Corresponding author:****Dr Saira Waqqar,**

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Please cite this article in press Saira Waqqar et al., *Risk Factors of Anxiety and Depression during Pregnancy*,
Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Anxiety is a state of confusion or disturbance, but depression is persistent feeling of sadness & worthlessness which affect the person's behavior, creativity, satisfaction, reduce their physical activity & sense of well being.(1) Pregnancy is natural event during which many biological and psychosocial changes occur.(2) Pregnancy is period of contentment & joyment; but in some women it can be a distressing event.(3) Antenatal A&D is the major health problem all over the world and its prevalence varies from 10-20% in developing countries.(1) Antenatal A&D is the most prevailing psychiatric disorder and it is consider as an important subject of public health due to many reasons. Depression during pregnancy is major risk factor for post-natal depression and it can also cause adverse Maternal & Fetal outcomes.(4) WHO estimates that depressive disorder will be the second leading cause of global disease burden by the year 2020. Women of reproductive age (14-49 years) are at high risk of having depressive disorder than that of men in same age range(5) In every woman's life pregnancy is a critical period in which she experiences several mental, physical, psychological, hormonal changes and due to these changes she suffer from depression. Symptoms of antenatal depression include; depressed mood, loss of interest, loss of concentration and feeling of low self-esteem. These symptoms are same as depression in general population. Antenatal depression is the predictor of post partum depression and PPD leads to serious consequences for women's life and cause behavioral disorders, poor interaction and physical impairment in child's life. (6) There is strong relationship between antenatal depression and deprived child outcomes in low & middle income population. Antenatal depression is most common in mid & late trimester.(7)

There are several risk factors of antenatal depression & anxiety these includes; Lack of Socioeconomic status Younger age of mothers, Living alone, Disharmony between couples, Poor Nutrition, Gender-Base Violence, History of Miscarriage, Gravidity, Unplanned Pregnancy, Poor Education level, Low Income, Poor marital relationship, Lack of social support and long period of infertility.(2-4) Researches show that there is a connection between antenatal depression & postnatal depression. 50% women of postnatal depression were those who had depression before or during pregnancy. These studies report that in developed countries rate of antenatal depression during second & third trimester was (13% & 12%) respectively.(8) Literature shows that all over the world, pregnant women have high prevalence of psychiatric disorders. Mahboob et al,

compare antenatal depression among Pakistani and Canadian women and their study finding show high prevalence in Pakistani women (48%) as compare to Canadian women (31%).(3) Untreated depression leads to adverse maternal and child outcomes. One-third women take antidepressant as a treatment of antenatal depression. Literature shows women taking antidepressants during pregnancy were at higher risk of preterm birth as compare to women without depression. Non-pharmacological treatment is very effective for pregnant women like maternal education, counseling on routine checkup depressive symptoms screening etc. (9)

METHODOLOGY:

A case control study was conducted at DHQ Mianwali, THQ Talagang and Obaid Noor Hospital Mianwali. Study was conducted in 6 months duration (February- July 2018). Sample size was about 581 pregnant women and non-probability purposive sampling technique was used for sample selection. Women aged >18 to < 40, women their labor had not started, Consent to participate in the research and all type of gravidas & Para were included in this study while Females > 40 of age, who used psychiatric drugs during pregnancy, women with known psychiatric or neurological disorders, women having pregnancy related complications (placenta previa, preeclampsia, fetal distress etc.) all were excluded. Data was collected through A Self Structure Questionnaire composed of socio-demographic & obstetric baseline characteristics. Hospital Anxiety Depression Scale (HADS) was used to find out the level of depression & anxiety. The questionnaire comprises seven question for anxiety and seven questions for depression. Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) was used to measure perceptions of perceived social support from Family, Friends, and a Significant Other. Scale is comprised of total 12 items & 3 subscales. Each subscale having 4 statements. The lowest score to be obtained from each subscale is 4 whereas the highest score is 28. Data was analyzed through SPSS 21 and results were generated. Mean, standard deviations and percentages of all variables were calculated. Risk factors were evaluated by Odd Ratio (OR) with relevant 95% confidence interval. Results were explained in detail with the help of graphs and tables.

RESULTS:

Results of the study include physical characteristics, demographics, prevalence of Depression & Anxiety and associated Risk factors. In this study Mean age of participants was 25.93 ± 4.06 . Mean Height 5.18 ± 0.46 and Mean Weight 65.84 ± 10.25 of the study participants. BMI (body mass index) of patients was

also calculated, Mean BMI was 25.99 ± 3.52 . Patient's Demographics includes occupation, education & socioeconomic status, which were described and their graphically presentation

Frequency of Anxiety and depression was calculated by following formula;

No. of affected participant \div Total no. of patient \times 100

Study results show that out of 581 participants 193 cases were reported with anxiety and 177 with depression and remaining belongs to control group. Prevalence of anxiety was 33.21% and depression was 30.46%. In this study, Mean Anxiety score was 7.23 ± 3.27 and Mean Depression score was 7.35 ± 2.83 . Mean score of anxiety & depression indicate mild to moderate level of antenatal anxiety & depression.

Risk factors were calculated by Odd Ratio with 95% confidence interval. Results show that Antenatal Anxiety having higher odds with Family crises (6.98; CI: 4.57-10.64), Fear of Baby Girl (2.59; CI: 1.008-6.68), History of miscarriage (1.78; CI: 1.155-2.74) and Fear of C-Section (1.50; CI: 1.007-2.24).

Antenatal Depression having higher odds with Family crises (5.46; CI: 3.62-8.25), Fear of Baby Girl (3.74; CI: 1.43-9.86), History of miscarriage (2.31; CI: 1.49-3.573) and Fear of C-Section (1.786; CI: 1.19-2.68).

Bivariate correlation shows significant negative correlation between socioeconomic status, education, support from significant others, family support, friends support and anxiety ($r = -.236$, $p = .001$) ($r = -.160$, $p = .001$) ($r = -.157$, $p = .001$) ($r = -.293$, $p = .001$) ($r = -.140$, $p = .001$) respectively. While frequency of delivery shows significant positive correlation with anxiety ($r = .89$, $p = .031$). A significant negative correlation between socioeconomic status, education, support from significant others, family support, friends support and depression ($r = -.283$, $p = .001$) ($r = -.176$, $p = .001$) ($r = -.192$, $p = .001$) ($r = -.285$, $p = .001$) ($r = -.190$, $p = .001$) respectively but a significant positive correlation found between frequency of delivery and depression ($r = .182$, $p = .001$). BMI shows non-significant positive correlation with anxiety ($r = .038$, $p = .366$) and depression ($r = .028$, $p = .506$).

Table 11: shows Mean \pm S.D of physical characteristics of patients.

	Mean \pm S.D
Age(year's)	25.93 \pm 4.06
Height(feet's)	5.18 \pm 0.46
Weight(kg's)	65.84 \pm 10.25
BMI	25.99 \pm 3.52

Table 2: presents Level of Anxiety & Depression

		Frequency	Percentage	Mean \pm S.D
Anxiety	Control	388	66.8	7.23 \pm 3.27
	Case	193	33.21	
Depression	Control	404	69.5	7.35 \pm 2.83
	Case	177	30.46	

Table 3: show risk factor estimates of Antenatal Anxiety by Odd Ratio with 95% confidence interval.

		Anxiety Present		
		Control	Case	OR(95% CI)
Fear of C-Section	NO	310	140	1.50
	YES	78	53	
Fear of Baby Girl	NO	380	183	2.59
	YES	8	10	
History of miscarriage	NO	330	147	1.78
	YES	58	46	
Family crises last few months	NO	344	102	6.97
	YES	44	91	
Moral support from spouse	NO	7	44	0.62
	YES	381	194	

Table 4: show risk factor estimates of Antenatal Depression by Odd Ratio with 95% confidence interval.

		Depression Present		
		Control	Case	OR(95% CI)
Fear of C-Section	NO	326	124	1.78
	YES	78	53	
Fear of Baby Girl	NO	397	166	3.78
	YES	7	11	
History of miscarriage	NO	348	129	2.31
	YES	56	48	
Family crises last few months	NO	350	96	5.46
	YES	54	81	
Moral support from spouse	NO	9	42	0.073
	YES	395	135	

Table 5: show Bivariate correlation of variables with Anxiety & Depression.

	Scores of Anxiety		Scores of Depression	
	R	P	r	P
Socioeconomic status of Patient	r-.236	0.001	r-.283	0.001
Education of Patient	r-.160	0.001	r-.176	0.001
BMI	r.038	0.366	r.028	0.506
Frequency of delivery	r.89	0.031	r.182	0.001
Significant Others	r-.157	0.001	r-.192	0.001
Family Support	r-.293	0.001	r-.285	0.001
Friends Support	r-.140	0.001	r-.190	0.001

DISCUSSION:

Current study highlights the frequency of Anxiety & Depression during pregnancy, level of antenatal anxiety & depression and its associated risk factors. Results of current study show that by comparing two groups (one is case and other one is control group) anxiety was reported in 193 cases while 177 cases were reported with antenatal depression out of 581 participants. Study found frequency of antenatal anxiety was about (33.21%) & depression was (30.46%) by using HADS. Ahmad Waqas *et al*, (2015) were conducting cross-sectional study and found prevalence of antenatal depression (31%) & anxiety (49%).(3) Current findings show prevalence of antenatal anxiety was same to previously conducted studies in Pakistan but prevalence of antenatal depression was higher.

In current study (n=193) having anxiety and (n=177) having depression whereas, in previous study, Mechtilda Rwakarema *et al*,(2015) conducted a cross-sectional study were found 33.8% (n=134) prevalence of antenatal depression by using EPDS. Sawyer *et al*, conducted a systematic review studies were found mean prevalence of antenatal depression of about (11.3%) in 8 African countries.(5)

Niloufer S. Ali *et al*, (2012) were conducted hospital-based cross-sectional study to determine frequency of antenatal depression by using HADS. Results of their study shows (16.8%) having depression, (20.4%) having anxiety and (32.9%) participants suffering from both anxiety & depression. Hamirani *et al*, from Karachi were found antenatal depression (34.6%) by using EPDS. On the same participants by using ICD-10 diagnostic criteria Niaz *et al* were found low prevalence of anxiety & depression as compare to HADS.(10) Results of current study were much higher than previous study. Current study was case-control study with larger sample size. Lack of family support, gender based violence and history of miscarriage was might be the reasons for higher prevalence of antenatal depression & anxiety.

In current study mean anxiety score was (7.23±3.27) and Mean Depression score was (7.35±2.83). While previous study, Rahila Ghaffar *et al*, (2017) conducting a survey reported that mean anxiety score was (10.08±2.52) and mean Depression score was (9.51±2.55) which was very high due to increasing age of mothers, lack of formal maternal education and unemployment. Unemployment women have at higher risk of depression during pregnancy because house wives having more time to think about their pregnancy as compare to working women.(1) There is several risk factors of antenatal depression & anxiety,

current study mainly focus on Gender discrimination, History of miscarriage, Fear of C-Section, Family crises and social support. In current study OR shows that family crises were the major risk factor of antenatal anxiety & depression and after that gender discrimination were the leading cause because of lack of in-laws support, poor involvement in family matters and family preferences for baby boy. Previous study, Niloufer S. Ali *et al*, (2012) reported that Family problems due to lack of involvement in decision making, lack of husband support, poor relation with in-laws and gender discrimination were major risk factor of antenatal anxiety & depression.(10)

Songul Aktas (2015) previous study concluded that during pregnancy Social support from husband, family & friends provide comfort to pregnant women and make them emotionally & mentally strong so that they cope with anxious & stressful event of life. The same study focus on correlation between social support & antenatal anxiety & depression. Study findings show the highest mean score of significant others (24.63±5.29), mean score of family (24.10±5.59) and mean score of friends support (19.22±7.19).(2) In current study the total mean score of significant others (23.72±3.94), mean scores of family support (18.61±5.55) and mean scores of friends support (13.78±7.39). Findings of this study show that women got strongest social support from their husbands, secondly from family and very lowest support from their friends. Current study show significant negative correlation of all variables with anxiety & depression except frequency of delivery which show positive correlation with anxiety & depression. In previous study, Robert C Stewart *et al*,(2014) report poor social support is predictor of antenatal depression. Findings of their study show significant correlation between social support and antenatal depression & anxiety.(11) Nilam Shakeel *et al*,(2015) were report prevalence of antenatal depression among western European, south Asian, middle eastern and other groups. Their study shows that south Asian and middle eastern were at higher of antenatal depression. Study reported that prevalence of depression in middle east ranges from 19% to 57% and prevalence of antenatal depression from Pakistan was about 25% .(12) Suneth Buddhika Agampodi *et al*,(2013) reported antenatal prevalence of about(16.2%) in Anurdhapura, Sri Lanka. Which quite lower than other developing countries due to proper screening and intervention of maternal health problems and strong family support. Literature show higher prevalence in Bangladesh (33%), in Pakistan (25-48%) and in UK (30.7%).(13)

CONCLUSION:

Study concluded that one-third of pregnant women were reported with anxiety and depression. Findings of current study show that family crises were strongly associated with antenatal anxiety & depression while gender discrimination, history of miscarriage and fear of C-section were the other causes.

Conflict of Interest: Authors show no conflict of interest.

Funding: No funding was required in this study.

Ethical Approval: From Research Ethical Committee of Riphah College of Rehabilitation Sciences, Riphah International University Islamabad.

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